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Habitat and altitude preference of owlflies (Neuroptera) of Kerala, India

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Abstract: The work focuses on the habitat and altitude preferences of owlflies in the Kerala region based on the field collection data of five years. Among the five species reported from Kerala, *Glyptobasis nigrifrons* KIMMINS, 1949 and *Suphalomitus brevis* KIMMINS, 1949 prefer to occur only in forest habitats, and the remaining three species, i.e., *Ascalaphus abdominalis* (KIMMINS, 1949), *Ascalaphus sinister* WALKER, 1853 and *Glyptobasis dentifera* (WESTWOOD, 1847) prefer to occur both in synanthropic and forest habitats. Only *S. brevis* is found at high, mid and in low altitude regions. But a majority of species such as *A. sinister*, *A. abdominalis*, and *G. nigrifrons*, prefer mid and low-altitude regions. *Glyptobasis dentifera* is only seen in the low-altitude areas.

Key words: Neuroptera, Myrmeleontidae, Ascalaphinae, owlfly, Kerala.

INTRODUCTION

Owlflies belong to the subfamily Ascalaphinae (Family Myrmeleontidae) of Order Neuroptera. They comprise 438 species belonging to 100 genera (MACHADO *et al.* 2019; OSWALD 2025). Members of this subfamily, commonly referred to as owlflies, are medium-sized neuropterans characterized by large compound eyes and predominantly nocturnal adults although some genera are diurnal (e.g., *Libelloides*, *Deleproctophylla*) or crepuscular (e.g., *Bubopsis*, *Uluodes* (TJEDER 1992)). Owlflies occur mainly in warm, dry forests and grasslands, where they reach their highest diversity. In India, a total of 36 species belonging to 18 genera of owlflies are reported, among which only four species belonging to 3 genera are known from Kerala (SURYANARAYANAN & BIJOY 2021; WACHKOO *et al.* 2024).

Apart from species inventories, the habitat and altitudinal preferences of owlflies remain poorly studied in India. Such information is crucial for advancing future research on their taxonomy, ecology, biology, and conservation. In this work, the habitat and altitudinal preferences of Kerala's owlflies have been documented based on five years of field collection data. The findings provide a valuable baseline for guiding future field collections and studies on each species of owlfly from the region.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present study is based on five years of systematic fieldwork and specimen collection conducted between 2019 and 2024 across Kerala state, India. Approximately 40% of the Western Ghats, recognized globally as one of the hottest biodiversity hotspots, lies within the boundaries of Kerala, thereby offering a unique landscape for assessing insect diversity. The collections were carried out regularly using a circular sweep net and light trap (Mercury vapour bulb-160W). The collected specimens were killed using a killing jar with 2 to 3 drops of Ethyl acetate. Later, specimens were dried and held on entomological pins with proper labelling. The specimens were examined under a Labomed Luxeo 6Z Stereomicroscope and identified to the species level using taxonomic keys of KIMMINS (1949), GHOSH (2000), HASSAN & LIU (2021), and SURYANARAYANAN *et al.* (2024). The specimens were deposited in the insect collections of Shadpada Entomology Research Lab (SERL), Kerala, India.

Ascalaphids in Kerala inhabit a wide range of environments across altitudinal gradients from lowlands to montane regions (0–2000 m a.s.l.), under high annual precipitation (ca. 2000–4000 mm) and a prolonged monsoonal rainy season followed by a relatively dry period that favors adult activity. They are recorded from diverse ecosystems, including tropical wet evergreen, tropical moist and dry deciduous, and montane subtropical forests, as well as grasslands, plantation landscapes, and urban or rural habitats. Within these systems, ascalaphids are typically associated with open or semi-open microhabitats such as forest edges, clearings, and grasslands rather than closed-canopy interiors (TJEDER 1992).

Vegetation structure in these habitats is generally simple to moderately stratified (one to three vertical layers), with a well-developed herbaceous or shrubby layer that provides suitable perching sites. Substrates are typically well-drained, often sandy or rocky, with sparse to moderate ground cover. These habitats are predominantly natural to semi-natural in condition, although some species can persist in moderately disturbed environments.

The ecosystem preferences of each species were prepared based on the locality where it was collected. Collections were made either from forest ecosystems or from both forest ecosystems and synanthropic ecosystems of Kerala. Altitude preference of species was prepared based on the locality where it was collected. According to the Kerala Forests and Wildlife Department (<https://forest.kerala.gov.in/index.php/about-us/2022-11-29-07-11-17/forest-types>), the localities of Kerala are classified into different altitude regions: low (0-800m), medium (800-1450m) and high (1450-2000m). Based on this, the altitude preference of the species' is prepared.

RESULTS

A total of 5 owlflies belonging to 3 genera were collected from Kerala and are represented in the Table. 1. They include *Ascalaphus abdominalis* (KIMMINS, 1949), *Ascalaphus sinister* WALKER, 1853, *Glyptobasis dentifera* (WESTWOOD, 1847), *Glyptobasis nigrifrons* KIMMINS, 1949 and *Suphalomitus brevis* KIMMINS, 1949. Of this, *A. sinister* records for the first time from the Kerala region.

In this study, owlflies show preferences for certain ecosystems. The species like *G. nigrifrons* KIMMINS and *S. brevis* KIMMINS are collected only from forest ecosystems, while the species like *A. abdominalis* (KIMMINS), *A. sinister* WALKER and *G. dentifera* (WESTWOOD) are collected both from forest as well as synanthropic ecosystems (Table 2 and Fig. 1). None of the owlfly species prefer to occur only in a synanthropic ecosystem.

The species occurrence of Ascalaphinae is classified into three categories. They are I) Species seen in high, mid and low-altitude regions, II) Species seen in mid and low-altitude regions III) Species seen only in low-altitude regions. The categories like, I) Species seen only in high-altitude regions, II) Species seen in high and mid-altitude regions, III) Species seen in high and low-altitude regions, IV) Species seen only in mid-altitude regions, are absent in the Kerala region. So they are not included in Table 3. The majority of species like *A. sinister* WALKER, *A. abdominalis* (KIMMINS) and *G. nigrifrons* KIMMINS prefer mid and low-altitude regions. *G. dentifera* (WESTWOOD) are only seen in low-altitude regions, while *S. brevis* KIMMINS are found in high, mid, as well as low altitude regions (Table 3).

Tab. 1. Owlfly species in Kerala.

FAMILY MYRMELEONTIDAE	
Subfamily ASCALAPHINAE	
Genus <i>Ascalaphus</i> FABRICIUS	
1.	<i>Ascalaphus abdominalis</i> (KIMMINS, 1949)
2.	<i>Ascalaphus sinister</i> WALKER, 1853
Genus <i>Glyptobasis</i> MacLachlan	
3.	<i>Glyptobasis dentifera</i> (WESTWOOD, 1847)
4.	<i>Glyptobasis nigrifrons</i> KIMMINS, 1949
Genus <i>Suphalomitus</i> WEELE	
5.	<i>Suphalomitus brevis</i> KIMMINS, 1949

Tab. 2. Ecosystem preferences of owlfly species from Kerala.

Sl. No.	Species collected only from the forest ecosystem	Species collected from both the forest ecosystem and the synanthropic ecosystem	Species collected only from a synanthropic ecosystem
1.	<i>Glyptobasis nigrifrons</i> KIMMINS, 1949	<i>Ascalaphus abdominalis</i> (KIMMINS, 1949)	
2.	<i>Suphalomitus brevis</i> KIMMINS, 1949	<i>Ascalaphus sinister</i> WALKER, 1853	
3.		<i>Glyptobasis dentifera</i> (WESTWOOD, 1847)	

Tab. 3. Altitude preference of owlfly species from Kerala.

Sl. No.	Species seen in high, mid and low altitudes	Species seen at mid and low altitudes	Species seen only at low altitudes
1.	<i>Suphalomitus brevis</i> KIMMINS, 1949	<i>Ascalaphus sinister</i> WALKER, 1853	<i>Glyptobasis dentifera</i> (WESTWOOD, 1847)
2.		<i>Ascalaphus abdominalis</i> (KIMMINS, 1949)	
3.		<i>Glyptobasis nigrifrons</i> KIMMINS, 1949	

Fig. 1. Species occurrence of owlflies in the forest ecosystem and the synanthropic ecosystem..

DISCUSSION

Each owlfly species has its own microhabitats and altitude preferences (Tables 2 and 3). Most owl species in Kerala are found at mid or low altitudes. Compared with other insect orders, the Order Neuroptera has weak flight. This may be the reason for fewer occurrences of species in high altitude regions. But there are exceptions, *Suphalomitus brevis* KIMMINS is also seen in high altitudes. The exact reasons will be revealed only when the life cycle and biology of each species are studied. So each species' biology needs to be studied in detail to get a precise idea of the habitat and altitude preferences of owlflies.

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